

THE MAIN CULTURAL HERITAGE OBJECTS OF KARAKALPAK TOURISM

Jalgasbaeva Gulasal Maratovna

3rd year student at Karakalpak State University

Xojabaev Bawirjan Sansizbaevich

2nd year student at Karakalpak State University

Tursunbaeva Gawhar Bakbergen qizi

3rd year student at Karakalpak State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10618715>

Abstract: The article discusses the history of the key cultural heritage items that draw tourists to Karakalpakstan, along with its unique characteristics.

Key words: Tolstov, Shylpyk, Mizdakhan, Nazlimxan suliw, Yakubovskiy, Esbergenov, Topiraqqala.

We value the land that is between the two major rivers, Joyhun and Soyhun. This location is the birthplace of our ancient culture and heritage. It is a sacred land where scientists from all over the world raise thinkers. Our ancestors, who lived on the islands of two rivers, built fortresses and cities for thousands of years before the new era, laid the groundwork for agricultural knowledge and experience, and fought external enemies and natural disasters with their skill

" I.Karimov The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "

The cultural heritage of Karakalpakstan is rich. Our historically noteworthy land is home to a large number of defenses and mausoleums of various forms. Approximately one thousand historical artifacts have been discovered in Karakalpakstan's region, according to recent research. In opposition to Tilak, about 700 of them vanished. This vast area was dubbed "the second Egypt between two rivers" by archaeologist Sergey Tolstov, who started studying our territory in 1938. Many historical artifacts are currently undergoing renovations as a result of the emphasis on tourism. Tourists are drawn to these kinds of opportunities. Some of our most precious cultural legacies are located in such amazing places as Hakim ata Mausoleum in Moynaq district, the Mizdakhan archaeological complex in Khojeli district, the Erejep Khalifa madrasa, Tuproqkala, Qirraqizkala monuments in Ellikkala district, Dawit ata mausoleum in Qonirat district, and Shylpiq monument in Amudarya district.

Every tourist who wants to travel to Karakalpakstan is first of all interested in our historical memories. Below, we will consider some cultural heritage objects that are worthy of attention in our country and have their place in our tourism.

Shilpik. The Sultan Ways, sometimes called Qarataw, are a group of mountains located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan's central region. Shilpik, Qara to'be and Bes to'be are among the strewn hills along the Amudarya, to the northwest of this peak. Like Qarataw, each of these topics has a past and secrets of its own. Especially, Shylpyk Hill is situated differently among them. Situated in the country's Amiwdaya area, this memorial has been the focus of scholarly research. Situated on top of a natural hill 43 miles from Nukus, Shylpiq is a round tower with a diameter of 65 meters and a height of 15 meters. It is recognized as an old Zoroastrian monument.

A. E. Rostsikova, a Russian travel scientist, who got to know Shylpyk closely, in 1902, when she told the local people that the monument is located on the river bank and is very well located on a high hill. Among them, it is said that there are Arabic inscriptions, some hieroglyphic inscriptions, incomprehensible inscriptions on the walls and rocks. According to the opinion of ethnographer H. Eshbergenov, the deceased were brought to Shylpyk, first according to Zoroastrianism, then according to the principles of Islam. Shylpyk was one of the most important places of praying on the South Aral coast. Young couples, childless women, sick people visited it. Until the beginning of the 20th century, folk dances were held in Shylpyk in connection with Navruz and Kurban Eid holidays.

Prominent figure in the history of Central Asian architecture, Dr. S.M. Bulatov, who conducted inspection work in Shylpyk in 1990, thinks this is where the astronomical research took place. By using the "Mysterious Door" with its strong walls on the right side of the memorial walls, observations were performed on the astronomical equipment set up in the snow, based on the professor's calculation

It was discovered and researched the Tuproqkala monument, a significant piece of historical heritage from the Kungirotdistrict. Under the direction of S. P. Tolstov, the historic capital of Khorezm b. It was relocated to Pil Castle starting in the IV century, as evidenced by the fact that it was Tuproqkala in the II-III centuries. However, this search proved fruitless in the years that followed. The reason for this is that their investigations, which went on throughout the ensuing years, showed that Tuproqkala was actually a dynastic center devoted to the state's religious rites rather than the capital. The architectural structure is 500 by 350 meters. It is four corners, dug out of the castle's surface, and covered with walls that rise to a height of eight or nine meters.

Towers were built down the length of the palace, one at each corner. Beginning at the head of the castle, the street wall was split into two sections. One side of the street was full with temple buildings, while the other was divided into quarters, primarily occupied by craftsmen. Gold bracelet with a mountain ram's horns discovered in one of the city's structures, surrounded by a plethora of glass jars, ornamental items, olebaster (sculpture) figures, paintings on paper depicting men in masks weeping, soldiers in the "Hall of Soldiers" and kings in the "Hall of Kings" cast in uncooked clay. Additionally, travelers visiting our country were drawn to the enigmatic Nazlimxansuliw architectural edifice.

Nazlimxan suliw. This memorial brought back our people's priceless Middle Ages memories. It is a part of the Mizdakhan archeological complex in the Khojeli area. One of the first researchers to study this site was Professor A. Yu. Yakubovsky. It is believed to be a subterranean mausoleum from the late 13th and early 14th centuries. Nazlimxan suliw's exquisite mausoleum is a semi-subterranean architectural monument. The main branch of the mausoleum, which leads to the vaulted hallway, is below ground, although the gateway and dome are above it. The square-shaped center hall of the tomb is topped by an octagonal dome featuring one shallow step and deep ends. Bows in the color sky blue adorn the mausoleum's walls.

Up until recently, Persian inscriptions embellished with blue mosaic tiles were preserved on the stone above this tomb. A portion of the epigraphic inscription there, according to the scientist A. Nekrasov, says, "Hey, man... If you are proud of me!" Don't assume that I'm miserable in the hereafter. You should know that I'm in heaven and that I'm pleased there.

The locals refer to the memorial as "Girl's house" or "Sufism girl's house." The structure, which measures 30 by 30 meters overall, was constructed in a distinctive architectural style.

It's easy to see the memory dome at a glance. Numerous inscriptions and designs adorn the building's inside. There are areas with a semi-domed top and a transparent platform on the north and east edges of the center hall. They both have pipes. The stories say that the one in the east belongs to a young man named Abutalib, who constructed this structure, while the one in the north is owned by a stunning girl named Nazlimxansuliw. Despite the fact that the girl's father did not give her to a boy, these two are in love. The kid and the girl will eventually leave this facility and return. Based on these stories, Nazlimxansuliw can be interpreted as a representation of love.

In general, many recollections may be mentioned when discussing the cultural heritage items of Karakalpakstan. Many of them, though, are in an emergency. If numerous monuments undergo renovation, there's no doubt that more people will travel to our country.

References:

1. G. Hojaniyazov " Қарақалпақстандағы муқаддес орынлар " - Nukus - 1994 [4-12 p]
2. Ё. Hojaniyazov, J. Hakimniyazov " Қаралалпақстанның әжайип жети естелиги " Nukus - 2004 [11-29 p]
3. Yagodin V. N., Holjayov T. K., Некрополь древнего Миздакхана Т-1970